

Implementation of Self Addressing RAM

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Abstract:- This paper aims to implement a RAM which can address itself to load the data into its memory. Using Xilinx 14.1 ISE for simulation and synthesis the RAM of size 16 x 32 is implemented with consecutive addresses generated automatically by the additional circuit in the design.

Keywords:- RAM, BRAM, Single Port BRAM, Dual Port BRAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic memory structures are divided into RAM and ROM. The RAM, also known as Read/Write memory is capable of both Read and Write operations, whereas ROM is read only and can be useful in program memory of a computing system. The basic operations in a RAM requires an enable signal for both read and write operations, clock for synchronization and data to be written into memory locations. The address decoders are needed to reach the memory locations in the memory for both operations which significantly increases the complexity of the design.

II. BRAMS IN FPGAS

Xilinx FPGAs provide SelectRAM memory blocks that can be utilized for implementing RAM, ROM, FIFO, CAMs, large look up tables, buffers, shift registers etc. The Spartan family of devices supports two configurations of memories such as Dual Port RAMs and Single Port RAMs. The BRAMs when used in dual port configuration have two independent access ports which support read and write data operations. Each port has its own clock and enable signals. If used in single port configuration, it has only one set of clock and enable signals as shown in the fig1 and Fig 2.

Fig. 1: Single Port BRAM

Utilizing these configurations we can implement variety of applications that involves memories, such as FIFO, CAM, ROM, etc.

III. ALGORITHM

In this paper we discuss the algorithm that implements a RAM that does not require address generation by address decoders that are commonly found in any memory implementations. Instead it relies on self addressing scheme where each location of the memory is addressed by data itself which is part of any location. Therefore data that we refer here is partly actual data that we store in a location and additional bits that act as an address for next location. The overall algorithm is shown in Fig 3.

Fig. 3: Block Diagram of Self Addressing RAM

The Multiplexer block selects the Base address which is the address from where we need to write the data in to the memory or next address where data is to be written into the memory. Array block stores the set of data values to be written into RAM at different locations. And RAM block

